

WORD DOMAINS

176 Mapudungun

I. Segmental properties

1. Segmental properties

§ Syllable structure: (C₁) V (C₂)

C₁ can be any consonant or glide (except the glide *g* /ɣ/)

V can be any vowel (all of which are short)

C₂ can be only a continuant segment

(i.e. plosives and affricates are excluded from the coda)

§ The vowel *ü* /^h/ appears only on roots or as epenthesis

§ *ü* /^h/ has two allophones: [ˆ] when stressed and [˘] when unstressed (simplified)

§ Place of articulation of consonants in roots is basically free, but there is a constraint: alveolars and dentals do not cooccur

§ There are monosegmental (i.e. vocalic) verbal roots, but there do not appear to exist words like *a*, *e*, *i*, *o*, *u*, *ü* other than as interjections; words can be monosyllabic, nominal roots are typically, but not necessarily, di- or trisyllabic, verbal roots are typically mono- or disyllabic

§ Super heavy syllables or trimoraics are not admissible

2. Phonological processes

§ Word-final *o* /o/ is frequently realized as [u] (/u/ exists as a separate phoneme)

§ Word-initial *u* /u/, *i* /i/ and *ü* /^h/ frequently insert a (faint) homorganic glide *w* /w/, *y* /j/ or *g* /ɣ/ before them; somewhat less frequently, the same segments insert the homorganic glides after them in word-final position

§ All diphthongs can be realized as heterosyllabic vowel combinations in careful speech

§ Only morphophonemic rule: before the transitivizer suffix *-m*, *g* /ɣ/ → *k* /k/ and *f* /f/ → *p* /p/, e.g. *nag-i* [na.ɣi] ‘s/he went down’, *nak-üm-i* [na.k^h.mi] ‘s/he lowered it’

II. Prosodic properties

§ High, mid and low pitch is associated with primary, secondary and absent stress

§ Stress rules (= strong tendencies) bear relation to number and structure of syllables:

- 2 syllables: open ultima [ru.»ka] ~ [»ru.ka]
closed ultima [t@uf.»ken]
- 3 syllables: open ultima [ma.»wi.Ta]
closed ultima [«a.tSa.»waʔ]
- 4 syllables: open antepenult [ka.«ma.pu.»lei9] ~ [«ka.ma.pu.»lei9]
closed antepenult [we.«jul.k'.»lei9]
- 5+ syllables: open 2nd syllable

[«wa.su.tu.ku.lel.Ne.ke@.»kei9] ~
 [wa.«su.tu.ku.lel.Ne.ke@.»kei9]
 closed 2nd syllable

[p'.«n5an5.tu.ku.lel.Ne.ke@.»kei9]

- with *-fi*: [«le.li.»fi.mi] rather than [«le.li.fi.»mi] *-fi* = 30
- in NPs: heads, i.e. [kom#»tSe], [tatSi#»wa], [»ko#mew], [»e#»pun5]

§ Some adverbs with a CVCV(C) structure have lexically assigned stress on the ultima

III. Morphosyntax

§ I have not found any allomorphy that violates adjacency conditions or that goes across words

§ There is no infixation; most affixation is suffixation, with some minor prefixation and, depending on the analysis, possibly some simulfixation in the verb as well. Most, but not all, affixes lack consonantal codas. There do not seem to be systematic differences between prefixes and suffixes with respect to segmental or prosodic constraints.

§ There is root serialization with verbs, where up to 3 roots (typically 2) form a complex predicate stem; the functional yield is of the ‘up’, ‘out’ etc. type, but also causative, desiderative, etc.

§ Reduplication: for iterative verb forms; whole verb stem is reduplicated

rüŋkü-y ‘s/he jumped’

rüŋkü-rüŋkü-tu-y ‘s/he jumped repeatedly, bounced’

There is no segment mutation, although there can be epenthesis if clusters result

The resulting forms fully conform to the phonotactic and prosodic properties

§ We still know too little on clitics and particles ☹

IV. Other questions

§ Unstressed vowels: cf. [ˆ] vs. [ˊ] allomorphy for ü / ʉ/

§ There are no bipartite stems that I am aware of

§ There is only one “periphrastic” form, viz. one of the progressives:

petu lef-i (still run-IND) ‘s/he is running’

§ Prepositions: little information. They do not seem to form intonational unit with NPs

§ Postpositions: they frequently, but not necessarily, force stress:

ruka [ru.»ka] ~ [»ru.ka] ‘house’, but *ruka mew* [ru.»ka#mew] ‘in the house’